

APPLICATION OF WEIBULL ANALYSIS TO THE DISTRIBUTION OF FAILURE STRENGTH IN BULK SAMPLES OF AN EPOXY MATRIX

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ABSTRACT

The distribution of tensile strengths within samples of a commercial epoxy resin has been studied by fabricating novel sandwich laminates consisting of a bulk resin core with two outer $[0^\circ]$ GFRP laminates. Experiments were carried out using sandwich laminates with cores of three different thicknesses in the range of 0.6 to 2.4mm. The laminates were tested in tension and the individual transverse cracking events in the resin core were used to construct Weibull strength distribution plots. Weak link scaling was then applied to correlate the laminate data with results from conventional coupon tensile tests of the resin. Extrapolation of the statistical data to small volumes of matrix (representative of those existing between fibres in practical composites) suggest the potential for localised plastic deformation of the matrix.

KEY WORDS: Epoxy resin; Matrix; Strength distribution; Weibull statistics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Unidirectional reinforced fibre composites possess high specific strength and stiffness in the fibre direction. However, their strength under off-axis loading is significantly lower. In most structural applications some degree of biaxial performance is required and fibres need to be oriented to support these stresses. In laminates containing both axial and off-axis plies, first ply failure occurs in these off-axis plies at strains much lower than the failure strains of the 0° plies. In cross-ply laminates in particular cracks form perpendicular to the principal loading direction as a result of matrix fracture and/or fibre/matrix debonds in the same plane.

Although at a global (ply) level transverse failure may be described using macroscopic (ply level) fracture mechanics(1), at a micro-mechanical level the fracture path will usually involve matrix failure and fibre/matrix interface failure. To model these processes in detail it is important to understand the fracture behaviour of the matrix in situ and in particular the range of initial defect sizes which are present.

Many workers have addressed the phenomenon of 90° ply cracking in glass and carbon systems(2-6). In particular Manders et al(4) have studied the distribution of crack spacings in 0/90/0 glass/epoxy laminates and demonstrated that a model based on a unique value of strength in the 90° ply was inadequate to account for the observed spacing. They proposed a statistical description of the crack spacing based on a Weibull distribution which could be used to explain the size effect and was also more appropriate at low strains (large crack spacing). They argued that variations in the strain magnification factor caused by the fibre

packing could be responsible for the strength distribution shown by the 90° ply. These workers did not consider the contributing effects of inherent matrix defects which are addressed in the present paper. Peters and co-workers(5,6), investigated transverse ply cracking in CFRP cross-ply laminates under tensile loading. They assumed a Weibull distribution for the fracture strain. Based on this analysis Peters(6) found that the shape factor of the derived two parameter Weibull distribution for transverse ply strength was ply-thickness dependent. He attributed this to the differing degree of constraint imposed on flaws present close to the 0/90 interface compared to that seen by flaws located towards the centre of the ply.

In this work the process of "brittle" tensile failure is studied using a novel sandwich laminate in which a core layer of resin is constrained by outer layers of glass fibre reinforced resin, permitting multiple fracture of the resin core under applied tensile loading. The data are analysed using Weibull statistics which is applicable to describe the strength of any brittle solid with the assumption that the flaws are self similar but differ in severity and are distributed randomly in the bulk.

2. Materials and Fabrication

The epoxy system investigated was a tetra-functional resin based on tertraglycidyl diamino diphenyl methane (TGDDM), cured with diamino diphenyl sulphone (DDS), a difunctional primary amine curing agent. The formulation also contains some boron trifluoride monoethyl amine adduct (BF₃.MEA) as catalyst. To manufacture the sandwich laminates, plaques of the bulk resin were cast between glass plates and surface ground to various thicknesses (i.e. 0.6, 1.2 and 2.4 mm). The plaques were then placed between layers of unidirectional glass fibre wound on to a rectangular frame. Shell Epikote 828 (DGEBA) resin cured with nadic methyl anhydride (NMA) and benzyl dimethyl amine (BDMA) accelerator was used as the matrix for the glass fibre layers. It was necessary to use the 828/NMA system in the outer plies since the strain to fracture of the TGDDM resin would be insufficient to enable the test to be conducted - the outer plies must have substantially higher strain to failure than the core to induce multiple core fracture. Furthermore, the glass/828/NMA system is highly transparent which allows the cracking in the core layer to be readily observed. After the impregnation of this resin into the glass layers on either side of the plaque, the whole sandwich laminate was cured for 3 hours @ 100°C. Two glass plates under pressure ensured dimensional consistency. 20mm wide coupons were cut from the laminate, end-tagged and strain gauged prior to mechanical testing.

During loading regular photographic records were obtained in order to produce a clear account of failure strain and location for each individual cracking event. The data were used to conduct Weibull statistical analysis as described in Section 4.

3. Observations of Matrix Cracking in Sandwich Laminates

Figure 1 illustrates failed specimens of the various 0°/matrix/0° laminates, which bear close resemblance to transversely cracked 0/90/0 GFRP laminates(2,4). In all samples two types of cracking can be seen. Simple two dimensional cracks, oriented perpendicular to the applied stress and spanning the width and thickness of the matrix layer, appear at lower strains (i.e. typically below 2.2 % strain for the 0.6 mm core, 1.4 % strain for 1.2 mm core, and 0.9 % strain for the 2.4 mm core) whereas more complex-shaped multi-crack combinations appeared at higher strains. The occurrence of these complex cracks may be attributed to dynamic effects associated with sudden strain energy release at the time of fracture. This effect will be magnified with increasing core thickness and also higher applied strains. Similar effects of larger transverse cracking events (i.e. transverse cracking accompanied by multiple ≈45° neighbouring cracks) and localised delamination for thicker transverse ply thicknesses have

been reported by Parvizi and Bailey(2) in their studies of cross-ply laminates.

4. Statistical Analysis of Matrix Cracking Data

Figure 2 is a SEM micrograph of a typical tensile bulk fracture surface in the resin. The fracture has initiated from an internal foreign-body inclusion and is surrounded by the generically named mirror, mist and hackle features in series. Similar fracture surface features are observed with other notch-sensitive glassy and brittle materials and are indicative of changes in cracking velocity as determined by the magnitude of the stress intensity at the propagating crack front. Based on such observations it is suggested that the failures in the bulk resin are attributable to randomly distributed flaws of different size leading to the observed scatter in tensile strength and this is the physical basis for assuming that the strengths can be described by a Weibull distribution. To analyse the cracking in the core of the sandwich samples we proceed as follows. The core layer is considered to consist of small elements which are connected in series. The length of these elements needs to be chosen such that each breaks only once during the course of the test on the sandwich laminate. Each break leads to a localised non-uniform stress state such that the longitudinal stress in the core builds up from zero at the crack to a large fraction (often taken as 90 %) of its undisturbed value, over a distance regarded as half the "ineffective length". A model based on a shear-lag analysis can be applied to calculate this length(5,6).

Peters et al(5,6) have shown that the calculated ineffective length is of the same order as the 90° ply thickness in cross-ply laminates. Manders et al(4) reached a similar conclusion based upon statistical interpolations and observations of stress whitening either side of a crack in their specimens. For the present study it was decided to choose segment lengths (i.e. portions of gauge length where only a single failure is expected at saturation) of 0.6, 1.2, and 2.4 mm for the Weibull analysis. The choice of these values facilitates comparison of the different core thicknesses at constant volume. Moreover, close examination of the failed samples confirmed that the final crack spacings were approximately of the correct order. The segment length, L_s , is important since it governs the maximum number of matrix failures that can be expected during a test, N , where $N = L/L_s$ with L being the test gauge length. Having chosen L_s (and hence N) the probabilities of failure associated with each matrix fracture event during the sandwich laminate test can be obtained as outlined below.

The stress/strain data and photographic records made during each test were used to determine the applied mechanical strain at which each fracture event occurs. The differential thermal expansion between the neat epoxy core and the GFRP laminae results in a residual thermal tensile strain in the core which is treated as simply additive to any externally applied strain. The calculated strain, ϵ_{Th} , was of the order of 0.3 % for all the sample configurations in the presented results.

The failure strain data (in ascending order) were nominated a ranking number, n_i , in the range 1 to n where n is the number of fractures at test termination. The probability of failure associated with each failure event was then calculated simply from the ratio $n_i/(N+1)$. The data can then be presented as conventional Weibull plots of $\ln\{\ln[1/P_s(V_0)]\}$ against $\ln(\epsilon_f)$ from which the characteristic strain (for which the survival probability = 37 %) and Weibull modulus (slope) can be determined. In instances when the expected number of segment failures was much greater than the observed events at the test saturation strain (n), the characteristic and mean (survival probability = 50 %) strength values were obtained by extrapolation of the regression lines to the appropriate probability levels.

5. Strength Distributions and Weibull Analysis

Figure 3 illustrates a set of Weibull strength distribution charts for the 1.2mm core thickness

sandwich. The figure consists of three individual charts relating to the three chosen segment lengths. **Table 1** lists values for the mean failure strain ϵ_m , characteristic failure strain ϵ_0 , and the Weibull shape parameter, W , for each of the three core thicknesses at the three different segment lengths. The shape parameter is seen to increase slightly with decreasing core thickness. Peters and Andersen(5) have observed a more marked trend with reducing 90° ply thickness which, as noted earlier, was explained in terms of the constraining effects of the 0° ply, suppressing failure of the population of flaws at or near the interface and therefore leading to reduced variability. This may also be a consideration here, but is perhaps likely to be less important for two reasons. Firstly, the critical flaw size for unconstrained resin fracture may be smaller than the corresponding flaw size for 90° ply failure. Secondly, the ply thicknesses here are greater than those used by Peters (6) so that the influence of the constrained layer close to the 0° interface will be correspondingly less.

The shape parameters were obtained from the slopes of regression lines through all the data points; however, the data points obtained towards the end of the test are subject to possible interaction with neighbouring cracks, especially brought about by the complexity of the cracking events. Therefore, the W values are likely to be somewhat underestimated, especially for the thicker core dimensions. The variability of the 2.4mm core results (as noted by its low Weibull modulus) is a cause for concern. The magnitude of the change when compared with the other sets of data suggest that the increased variability may be due to factors other than reduced 0° constraint or the size effect. It is suggested that the most likely reason is an increase in the importance and relative magnitude of dynamic events since the energy release will be greatest in the thickest ply. It is interesting to note that the results obtained by assuming a 2.4 mm segment length display slightly less variability (i.e. W increases) and this may be attributed to the lessening importance of crack interaction if a large segment length is assumed.

The mean failure strains (ϵ_m) values were used to construct weak link scaling (WLS) graphs in which $\ln(\epsilon_m)$ is plotted against natural log of either sample gauge-length or volume of gauge section. **Figure 4** is an example of the WLS graph based on the gauge-volume. The mean and standard deviation corresponding to standard tensile tests using bulk resin dumb-bell coupons are also indicated for comparison. For each core thickness configuration the three mean values derived by using the three chosen segment lengths have been shown with common symbols and a straight line is used to distinguish the trends. In **figure 4**, the extrapolation of the sandwich laminate data come reasonably close to the bulk resin coupon data range.

The volume analysis of **figure 4** allows comparison of the different core thickness sandwich laminate results at constant volume. It can be seen that the mean fracture strain of the 1.2mm sandwich is lower than the equivalent volume 0.6mm sandwich. This may be another indication of the increased constraint imposed by the GFRP plies on the smaller core thicknesses or just due to scatter. A similar trend would have been expected from the thicker 2.4mm sandwich but is not seen; however, as discussed earlier this configuration suffers from anomalies (associated with complex cracking) which must reduce our confidence for the purpose of detailed direct comparison with the other data.

In usage of the data for prediction of the composite matrix properties it should be borne in mind that although Weibull's WLS prediction assumes a linear size effect for a plot of the type of **figure 4**, in reality there is likely to be a minimum plateau when beyond a certain volume of matrix samples, all samples will contain the same most severe critical flaw and hence further increases in volume do not result in further strength reductions. Conversely, a plateau must exist at the top end where the strength increase is limited by the yield point of the resin.

It is reasonable to imagine a scatter band encompassing all the sandwich and bulk data which could be used to form a predictive band subject to a possible error of estimated magnitude. The axes of the WLS charts have been extended to include a volume of the order of the inter-fibre spacing in a composite. This corresponds to a 2 μm fibre spacing for an ideal square array uniaxial carbon composite of $V_f=0.6$ (and the corresponding volume is a section

2 μ m high, 20mm long and 0.6mm wide). It can be seen that an extrapolated band predicts a strain to failure, ϵ_f , of the range 6% to 12% at this size. The yield point of the neat epoxy has been measured as 11.7% in compression. This can be converted and results in an estimated tensile yield strain of around 9% which matches conveniently with the mid-range value of the predicted composite matrix strength.

The main implication of the above interpretation is that the brittle resin has the potential of displaying plastic deformation in situ, provided that the fibre/matrix interfacial strength of the composite is capable of withstanding the stress. Limited fractographic evidence of matrix plastic deformation has been observed in post-mortem examination of various fibre reinforced composites. These observations are usually limited to resin rich regions where the strain magnification factor (SMF) is relatively low. At this juncture it is worth remembering that the analysis is probabilistic. The validity and applicability of the approach is the subject of an ongoing investigation which will include further bulk epoxy sandwich laminates of mid-range thickness values and the study of actual transverse failure of CFRP laminae.

5. Concluding Remarks

A valid estimate of strength distribution was generated using the novel GFRP/BULK RESIN/GFRP sandwich laminate method and Weibull statistics. The constraining effect of the 0° GFRP plies were considered by employing three values of core thickness. The technique highlighted here may be used to obtain the strength distribution and size effect of many brittle polymers and has the advantage of providing a large quantity of such data quickly using only a small number of test coupons. This may be of particular interest when qualifying new materials.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to acknowledge that the results presented in this report arose from participation in the PREDICT (Prediction of Damage Initiation and Growth in Composite Materials) which is a collaboration between British Aerospace, Ciba composites, Rolls Royce, AKZO Faser AG, National Physical Laboratory, University of Bristol and University of Surrey. The project is led by British Aerospace and is funded under the LINK Structural Composites programme of DTI's Research and Technology Initiative.

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Table 1: List of mean and characteristic strains and shape parameter from each of the Weibull plots.

Core Thickness	Mean Strain (ϵ_m)	Characteristic Strain (ϵ_0)	Shape Parameter (W)
<u>0.6mm Thick &</u>			
0.6mm Segments	3.33%	3.18%	7.91
1.2mm Segments	2.87%	2.97%	8.23
2.4mm Segments	2.57%	2.68%	9.19
<u>1.2mm Thick &</u>			
0.6mm Segments	2.62%	2.76%	6.84
1.2mm Segments	2.32%	2.44%	7.19
2.4mm Segments	2.02%	2.11%	8.72
<u>2.4mm Thick &</u>			
0.6mm Segments	2.81%	3.03%	4.86
1.2mm Segments	2.40%	2.59%	5.00
2.4mm Segments	2.04%	2.19%	5.16

Figure 1: Typical set of failed sandwich coupons. All samples shown have experienced a maximum tensile strain of $2.45 \pm 0.05\%$.

Figure 2: SEM fracture surface of a bulk epoxy tensile coupon.

Figure 3: Typical set of Weibull strength distribution plots. Results from the 1.2mm core thickness laminate at three different segment lengths.

Figure 4: Weak Link Scaling graphs. Analysis in terms of the gauge-volume.